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Proximate and Nutritional Composition of Locally Formulated Complementary Diets

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ABSTRACT

Infant malnutrition, particularly during the weaning period, remains a serious concern in developing countries due to limited access to affordable, nutrient-dense complementary foods. This study formulated and evaluated three weaning diets using locally sourced finger millet, soybean, unripe banana, sorghum bicolor leaf, pumpkin seeds, and dates. The nutritional quality of the formulated diets was compared with a commercial product (Cerelac®) and a maize-based control. Proximate analysis showed that the formulated diets had higher protein contents (Diet 1: 16.13%, Diet 2: 14.10%, Diet 3: 14.94%) compared to Cerelac® (14.00%) and maize (6.06%). Fibre content was significantly higher in the formulated diets (Diet 1: 14.07%, Diet 2: 15.87%, Diet 3: 13.80%) relative to Cerelac® (4.98%) and maize (5.48%). The mineral composition analysis showed that Diet 2 had the highest level of Calcium (Ca) (91.22 mg/100g), Magnesium (Mg), (142.81 mg/100g), and Zinc (Zn) (17.73 mg/100g), as compared to Cerelac; Ca (49.03 mg/100g), Mg (17.03±0.01 mg/100g), and Zinc (11.30±0.01 mg/100g). The vitamins composition analysis indicate that Diet 2 had the highest Vitamin C (Ascorbic Acid) and Vitamin B2 (Riboflavin) contents, while Diet 3 had showed the highest content of Vitamin B1 (Thiamine), Vitamin B6(Pyridoxine), and Vitamin B3 (Niacin). Fat content ranged from 4.38% to 7.46% in the formulated diets, with Diet 3 showing the highest fat content. Although the energy values of the formulated diets (300.49–318.42 kcal/100 g) were lower than Cerelac® (386.72 kcal/100 g), they remained nutritionally adequate. Essential amino acid profiles of the formulated diets met and exceeded WHO/FAO recommendations, with improved lysine (Diet 1: 4.55 g/100 g protein; Diet 2: 4.72 g/100 g protein) and tryptophan (Diet 1: 1.31 g/100 g protein; Diet 2: 1.39 g/100 g protein) contents compared to Cerelac and maize. Fatty acid analysis indicated a balanced distribution of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids, including linoleic (C18:2) and linolenic acids (C18:3), essential for infant growth. These results suggest that the formulated diets provide a cost-effective, locally available alternative to commercial weaning foods, with potential to address infant nutritional deficiencies in low-income settings.

Keywords: Weaning Diet, Infant Nutrition, Proximate Composition, Local Food Formulation, Amino acid Profile

1. INTRODUCTION

Infant malnutrition remains a significant health challenge in developing countries, contributing to high infant mortality, poor physical and intellectual development, and low disease resistance. This problem is especially critical during weaning, a transitional phase when children shift from breast milk to semi-solid foods and require energy-dense, nutrient-rich complementary diets to support rapid growth (Cameroon & Hofvander, 1971; Berggren, 1982; Sajilata et al., 2002; Umeta et al., 2003). However, in many developing

regions, high costs of protein-rich foods, limited availability, and traditional beliefs often result in nutritionally inadequate weaning practices.

Cereals and legumes, commonly available staples, can be combined to improve the amino acid content of complementary foods. Cereals are generally low in lysine but rich in sulfur-containing amino acids, whereas legumes are lysine-rich but limited in sulfur amino acids (Tsai *et al.*, 1975; Wang & Daun, 2006; Iqbal *et al.*, 2006; Shewry, 2007). Supplementing cereal-based diets with legumes enhances the overall nutritional value.

In West Africa, typical weaning foods include cereals, starchy tubers, legumes, and vegetables. In Nigeria, fermented maize (akamu) and fermented garri (foo-foo) are common. Unlike fortified weaning foods used in developed countries, commercially fortified options in developing regions are often unaffordable. WHO recommends that complementary foods should provide adequate protein, high energy, low fibre, essential vitamins and minerals, and minimal anti-nutritional factors (WHO, 1998; WHO, 2000; WHO, 2001).

Despite growing research on locally formulated complementary foods (Nnam, 1998; Nnam, 2000; Nnam, 2001; FAO, 1997; Okoh, 1998), many traditional diets remain nutritionally deficient due to low nutrient density and high viscosity, leading mothers to dilute these foods, further reducing their nutritional value. Affordable, home-prepared weaning diets using local ingredients like finger millet, soybean, banana, sorghum bicolor leaf, pumpkin seeds, and date fruit may help address this issue.

This study, therefore, aims to develop and evaluate a nutrient-rich complementary food from these local ingredients to improve infant nutrition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

Finger millet grains, soybeans seeds, unripe plantain bunch, maize grains, dates, sorghum bicolor leaves and pumpkin seeds were bought from Rumuomasi market, in Port Harcourt, Rivers state.

Preparation Of Samples

Preparation of finger millet Grains Flour

Finger millet grains (*eleusine coracana* (1kg)) was sorted to remove stones, spoilt grains and other extraneous materials. The sorted finger millet grains were washed with clean water and soaked with water overnight for 24 hours, then it was drained and rinsed with clean water. The rinsed finger millets were tied in a sac bag and allowed to sprout for forty-eight hours (2 days) and then air dried. The dried grains were milled with local grinder and sieved with plastic sieve to fine powder, stored in an airtight Ziplock bag and labelled.

Preparation of soybeans flour

Soybeans seeds (1kg) were sorted to remove pebbles, stones and other extraneous materials. The seeds were washed and soaked for twelve (12) hours. The soaked soybeans seeds were drained and dehulled (by rubbing between the palms) and the hulls were removed by rinsing with clean water. The dehulled soybeans seeds were allowed to sprout for forty-eight (48) hours by spreading them on sac bag in the room and then air dried for 3 days, after which it was milled into flour with local grinder. The soybean flour was sieved with plastic sieve to fine flour and stored in an airtight Ziploc bag and labelled.

Preparation of Banana fruit flour

The unripe banana fruits (*Musa spp*) (one bunch) were washed with clean water and blanched, after which it was peeled manually, cut into slices of about 5mm thickness, dehydrated, milled and sieved into fine flour. The flour was packaged in an airtight Ziploc bag and labelled.

Preparation of sorghum bicolor leaf

The leaves were rinsed in clean water and air dried, milled with local grinder and sieved with plastic sieve to a fine powder then stored in a Ziploc bag.

Preparation of pumpkin seeds flour

Pumpkin seeds (500g) were sorted to remove stones and extraneous materials, milled with local blender and sieved with plastic sieve into fine flour. Packaged, labelled and stored in a Ziploc bag for further use.

Preparation of Dates flour

Dates fruits (500g) were rinsed with clean water and towel dried immediately to avoid water penetrating into the fruit, cracked with piston to remove the seeds, milled in a blender, sieved with plastic sieve, packaged in a Ziploc bag and labelled accordingly for further use.

Preparation of Maize grains flour

Yellow maize (1kg) grains were sorted to remove spoilt grains, stones and other extraneous materials. The grains were washed with clean water, soaked with water for 48 hours, germinated by spreading evenly on a sack bag in the room for 48 hours, air dried, milled with local grinder, sieved with plastic sieve to a fine flour and packaged in a Ziploc bag.

Table 2.1: Composition of flour formulations

Diets	Ratios	Percentage Composition
Diet 1	65FM:25SB:5BN:2.5SG:1.5PK:1.0D	95% major, 5% minor components
Diet 2	60FM:25SB:10BN:2.5SG:1.5PK:1.0D	95% major, 5% minor components
Diet 3	55FM:25SB:1.5BN:2.5SG:1.5PK:1.0D	95% major, 5% minor components
Standard	100	100% Cerelac®
Control 1	100	100% Maize
Control 2	100	100% rat chow

*Finger millet (FM): Soybean (SB): Banana (BN): Sorghum (SG): Pumpkin (PK): Dates (D)

Finger millet (carbohydrate), soybeans (protein), banana (vitamins, fiber), sorghum bicolor (iron), Pumpkin seeds (lipids, minerals), Dates (sweetener)

Proximate Composition

Determination of Moisture Content (method of AOAC (1984) was used)

A Petri-dish was washed and dried in a hot air oven at 100°C for 1 hour to obtain a constant weight and then cooled in a desiccator. Two grams (2g) of each of the samples were weighed into the different petri dishes and heated at 100°C for one hour. The result was noted and heated for another one hour until a constant weight was obtained and the weight was noted. Moisture content can be gotten from the formula below:

$$\% \text{ moisture content} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_2 - W_1} \times 100$$

Initial weight of the empty petri dish

W_2 = weight of petri dish + sample before drying W_3 = weight of petri dish + sample after drying

Determination of Crude Fat

Fat content was determined by the Soxhlet extraction method of AOAC (1984). This method was carried out by continuously extracting sample with non-polar organic solvent petroleum ether for about one hour or more. Clean boiling flasks of 250ml capacity were dried in the oven at 105-110°C for about 30 minutes and were transferred into a desiccator and allowed to cool. The boiling flasks were filled with 330ml of petroleum ether (boiling point of about 40-60°C). The extractor thimble was sealed with cotton wool. The Soxhlet apparatus was assembled and allowed to reflux for about 6 hours, after which the thimble was removed. When the flask is almost free of petroleum ether, it was removed and was dried at 105°C - 110°C for one hour in the oven. cooled in a desiccator and weighed.

Percentage fat was calculated using the formula below:

$$\% \text{ fat} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Where

W_1 = initial weight of flask and sample

W_2 = final weight of flask and sample

Determination of Crude Protein

This was determined using the micro-Kjeldahl method (AOAC, 1984). This method is the digestion of sample with hot concentrated sulphuric acid in the presence of a metallic catalyst. Organic nitrogen in the sample is reduced to ammonia. This is retained in the solution as ammonia sulphate; the solution is then distilled to release the ammonia. The ammonia is trapped in dilute acid and then titrated.

Exactly 0.5g of sample was weighed on a filter paper into a 30ml kjeldahl flask. The sample and the filter paper wrapped together and carefully dropped into the flask to avoid the sample from touching the walls of the flask, and then the flasks were stoppered and shaken. Then 0.5g of the kjeldahl catalyst mixture was added. The mixture in the flask was heated gently in a digestion rack until a clear solution was observed. The clear solution was allowed to stand for 30 minutes and left to cool. After cooling, about 100ml of distilled water was added to make up 100ml mark, and about 5ml of the digest was transferred to the kjeldahl distillation apparatus. A 100ml receiver flask containing 5ml of 2% Boric acid and indicator mixture containing 5 drops of Bromocresol blue and 1 drop of methylene blue was placed under a condenser of the distillation apparatus such that the outlet tip is below the surface of the boric acid. The 5ml of 40% sodium hydroxide was gently added to the digested sample in the apparatus. The trapped ammonia in the boric acid was titrated to pink colour using 0.01N hydrochloric acid. The level of the acid at which the colour changed was observed and recorded. The nitrogen content of the sample was calculated, the amount of nitrogen was multiplied by the factor 6.25 to obtain the crude protein content of the sample.

$$\% \text{Nitrogen} = \frac{\text{Titre} \times 0.01 \times 14 \times 4}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

$$\% \text{Protein} = \% \text{Nitrogen} \times 6.25 \text{ (where: } 6.25 \Rightarrow \text{Conversion factor of protein)}$$

Where

4 = Dilution factor

0.01 = Normality of HCl

14.01 = Atomic mass of nitrogen

Determination of Ash Content

Ash content was determined by AOAC (1984) procedure. The ash content of foodstuff is the inorganic residue remaining after the organic matter has been burnt away. It should be noted, however, that the ash obtained is not necessarily of the composition as there may be some from volatilization.

Empty platinum crucible was washed, dried and the weight was noted. Exactly 2g of wet sample was weighed into the platinum crucible and placed in a muffle furnace at 500°C for 3 hours. The sample was cooled in a desiccator after burning and weighed. Percentage ash was calculated using this expression:

$$\% \text{ Ash} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100$$

Where

W_1 = weight of empty platinum crucible

W_2 = weight of platinum crucible and sample before burning

W_3 = weight of platinum and ash

Determination of Crude Fibre

Crude fibre was determined by AOAC (1984) method.

Exactly 2g of the sample was defatted with petroleum ether (if the fat content is more than 10%). The boiled under reflux for 30 minutes with 200ml of a solution containing 1.25g of H₂SO₄ per 100ml of solution. The solution was filtered through linen or several layers of cheese cloth on a fluted funnel. Washed with boiling water until the washings are no longer acid. The residue was transferred to a beaker

and boiled for 30 minutes with 200ml of a solution containing 1.25g of carbonate free NaOH per 100ml. The final residue was filtered through a thin but close pad of washed and ignited asbestos in a Gooch crucible. It was dried in an electric oven and weighed. Incinerate, cool and weigh. Percent crude fiber was calculated using the expression.

The loss in weight after incineration x 100 is the percentage of crude fibre.

$$\% \text{ crude fibre} = \frac{\text{weight of fibre}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Determination of Carbohydrate Content (by difference)

The total carbohydrate content was estimated as the difference between 100 and the total sum of fat, moisture, fat, protein, crude fibre and ash as described by AOAC (2006).

Total carbohydrates (%) = 100— (%moisture + %fat + %protein + %crude fibre + %ash)

Determination of Energy Value kcal

The total energy or the caloric values was estimated by calculation using the water quantification factors of 4, 9 and 4 respectively for protein, fat and carbohydrate. The formula is Energy (in Kcal) 4 x (proteins and carbohydrates in grams) + 9 x fat in grams.

Determination of Mineral Contents

The mineral content analysis was conducted using Varian AA240 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer according to the method of APHA 1995 (American Public Health Association). (Adrian, 1973)

Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer principle is based on the sample being aspirated into the flame and atomized when the AAS's light beam is directed through the flame into the monochromator and onto the detector that measures the amount of light absorbed by the atomized element in the flame. Since metals have their own characteristic absorption wavelength, a source lamp composed of that element used, making the method relatively free from spectral or radiational interferences. The amount of energy of the characteristic wavelength absorbed in the flame is proportional to the concentration of the element in the sample.

Sample Digestion

Two grams of sample was weighed into a digestion flask and 20ml of acetic acid mixture (650ml conc HNO 80ml perchloric acid; 20ml conc H₂SO₄) was added. The flask was heated until a clear digest is obtained. The digest was diluted with distilled water to 100ml mark. Appropriate dilutions were then made for each element. The filtrate was analysed using FS240AA Agilent Technology.

Determination of Vitamin Content

Determination of Vitamin A

Vitamin A was determined by the calorimetric method of Kirk and Sawyer (1991). A measured weight (1g) of the sample and standard was mixed with 30ml of absolute alcohol and 3ml of 50° KOH solution was added to it and boiled gently for 30minutes under reflux. After washing with distilled water, vitamin A was extracted with 3x50ml of diethyl ether. The extract was evaporated to dryness at low temperature and then dissolved in 10ml of isopryl alcohol. 1ml of standard vitamin A solution prepared and that of the dissolved extract were transferred to separate cures and their respective absorbance were read in a spectrophotometer meter at 325nm with a reagent blank zero.

$$\text{Concentration of vitamin A in sample} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times \text{concentration of standard}}{\text{Absorbance of standard}}$$

Determination of Vitamin C (Ascorbic acid)

This was determined by the titrimetric method reported by (Kirk and Sawyer, 1991). A weighed sample was homogenized in 6% EDTA ITCA solution. The homogenate was filtered and used for analysis, 20ml of 30% KI solution was added to the homogenate followed by 100ml of distilled water, 1ml of 1% starch solution was added to it and it was titrated against 0.1M CUSO₄ solution. The end point was marked by a black coloration. A reagent blank was also titrated.

Vitamin content was calculated based on the relationship below. 1ml of 0.1M CUSO₄ 0.88mg
 Vitamin C mg/100 = $\frac{100 \times 0.88 \times \text{titre} - \text{blank}}{W}$

W

Determination of Vitamin E (Tocopherol)

This was determined by the flitter-mayer coulometric method reported by (Kirk and Sawyer, 1991). Exactly 1g of the sample was mixed with 10ml of ethanoic sulphuric acid and boiled gently under reflux for 30mins. It was transferred to a separating funnel and treated with 3x30ml diethyl ether and recovering ether layer each time, the ether extract was transferred to a desiccator and dried under for 30minutes and later evaporated to dryness at room temperature. The dried extract and equal volume of standard vitamin E were transferred to separate tubes. After continuous addition of 5ml of absolute alcohol and 1ml of concentrated nitric acid solution, the mixtures were allowed to stand for 5mins and the respective absorbance measured in a spectrophotometer meter at 410nm with blank reagent at zero.

Determination of Vitamin B₁ and B₂

Vitamin B₁ and B₂ were determined using the spectrophotometer method described by Kirk and Sawyer (1991). The sample (2g) was weighed into a conical flask and dissolved with 100ml of deionized water. It was shaken thoroughly, heated for 5minutes and allowed to cool and filtered. The filtrate was poured into a cuvette and their respective wavelength for the vitamins set to read the absorbance using spectrophotometer at 26nm for vitamin B₁ and 242nm for vitamin B₂ with blank reagent at zero.

$$\text{Concentration (mg)} = \frac{A \times D.F \times \text{volume of cuvette}}{E}$$

Where: A= absorbance

E = extinction coefficient =25 for B₁ and B₂

Determination of Vitamin B₃

This was determined by the titrimetric method described by (Kirk and Sawyer, 1991). Sample weighing 5g was dissolved in 20ml of anhydrous glacial acetic acid and warmed slightly. 5ml of acetic anhydride was added and mixed. Few drops (2- 3) of crystal violet solution was added as indicator. 0.1M perchloric acid was added to titrate to a greenish blue colour.

$$\text{Vitamin B}_3 = \frac{\text{titre value} \times 0.0122}{0.1}$$

DF = dilution factor= 5

Determination of Vitamin B₆

Vitamin B₆ was determined by the titrimetric method reported by (Kirk and Sawyer, 1991). Exactly 5g of sample was dissolved in a mixture of 5ml of anhydrous glacial acetic acid and 6ml of mercury 11 acetate solution. Two drops of crystal violet was added as indicator. 0.1M perchloric acid was used to titrate to green colour end point.

Determination of Fatty Acids

The gas chromatography – flame ionization detection (GC-FID) method was used. 5 mg of the test sample was diluted with 1 ml of hexane and transferred into a test tube. 50 µl of sodium methoxide was pipetted into the sample in the test tube and vortex mixed. The sample solution was incubated for 5 minutes in a room temperature, after which it was centrifuged at a speed of 1600 rpm for 5 minutes. Results of peak profile for each sample obtained were recorded and compared with a standard.

Determination of Amino Acids

Preparation of samples and standards

Prior to derivatization, sample proteins were hydrolysed as follows. A 0.1-g lyophilized sample was weighed into a 16- x 125-mm screw-cap Pyrex (Barcelona, Spain) tube, 15mL of 6N hydrochloric acid was added, and the tube was thoroughly flushed with N₂, quickly capped, and placed in an oven at 110°C for 24h (17). After hydrolysis, the tube contents were vacuum filtered (Whatman #541, Maidstone, England) to remove solids, the filtrate was made up to 25 mL with water, and an aliquot of this solution

was further filtered through a 0.50-µm pore-size membrane (Millipore, Madrid, Spain). A standard solution containing 1.25 µmol/mL of each amino acid in 0.1N hydrochloric acid was created. The procedure used was a modification of the method of Elkin *et al.*, (1985). A standard solution (5, 10, 15, or 20 µL) or 50 µL of sample solution was pipetted into a 10- x 5-mm tube and dried in vacuo at 65°C. To the residue, 30 µL of methanol-water-Phenylisothiocyanate (2:2:1 [v/v]) was added and then removed in vacuo at 65°C. Next, 30 µL of the derivatizing reagent methanol-water-Phenylisothiocyanate (7:1:1:1 [v/v]) was added, and the tube was agitated and left to stand at room temperature for 20 minutes. Finally, the solvents were removed under a nitrogen stream, and the tube was sealed and stored at 4°C, pending analysis. Prior to injection, 150 µL of diluent consisting of 5mM sodium phosphate with 5% acetonitrile was added to each tube. Chromatography was carried out at a constant temperature of 30°C using a gradient elution as follows. Eluant A was an aqueous buffer prepared by adding 0.5 mL/L Triethylamine to 0.14M sodium acetate and titrating it to pH 6.20 with glacial acetic acid; eluant B was acetonitrile-water (60:40 [v/v]).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proximate Composition

The formulated diets had higher protein content (14.10–16.13%) than maize (6.06%) and slightly exceeded Cerelac® (14.00%), largely due to soybean and pumpkin seed inclusion. This meets WHO/FAO recommendations for complementary foods, essential for infant growth.

Fiber content (13.80–15.87%) was significantly higher than Cerelac® (4.98%) and maize (5.48%). This may be due to the high fiber content of unripe banana and sorghum bicolor leaves. While excess fiber can reduce energy density, the levels here remain acceptable and may support digestion.

Ash content, indicating mineral presence, was higher (2.80–3.30%) compared to Cerelac® (1.60%) and maize (1.15%), suggesting better mineral provision.

The moisture content of the formulated weaning diet (6.22 - 8.88%) was significantly higher than the moisture content of the reference diet Cerelac (2.60±0.03 g/100g). However, the moisture content of the diet was below 10% which is the acceptable maximum level by FAO.

The carbohydrate content of the formulated complementary diet (6.82 - 55.55%) was lower as compared to the reference Cerelac® (72.60 ± 0.22%).

The energy values (300.49–318.42 kcal/100 g) were slightly lower than Cerelac® (386.72 kcal/100 g) but sufficient, especially when complemented with energy-dense foods like oil or milk.

Table 2.1: Proximate Composition (%) of the Formulated Diets, reference diet and basal diet

Proximate Parameters	Cerelac®	Maize	Diet 1	Diet 2	Diet 3
Moisture Content %	2.60 ± 0.03 ^a	14.13 ± 0.01 ^{bc}	8.88 ± 0.01 ^{bd}	6.22 ± 0.04 ^{bd}	8.69 ± 0.09 ^{bd}
Ash Content %	1.60 ± 0.06 ^a	1.15 ± 0.03 ^{bc}	2.80 ± 0.05 ^{bd}	2.90 ± 0.00 ^{bd}	3.30 ± 0.06 ^{bd}
Fibre Content %	4.98 ± 0.01 ^a	5.48 ± 0.06 ^{ac}	14.07 ± 0.17 ^{bd}	15.87 ± 0.04 ^{bd}	13.80 ± 0.46 ^{bd}
Fat Content %	4.48 ± 0.17 ^a	3.00 ± 0.00 ^{bc}	5.57 ± 0.23 ^{bd}	4.38 ± 0.12 ^{ad}	7.46 ± 0.17 ^{bd}
Protein Content %	14.00 ± 0.00 ^a	6.06 ± 0.00 ^{bc}	16.13 ± 0.00 ^{ac}	14.10 ± 3.44 ^{ac}	14.94 ± 0.00 ^{ac}
Carbohydrate Content %	72.60 ± 0.22 ^a	70.19 ± 0.05 ^{bc}	49.46 ± 0.07 ^{bd}	55.55 ± 0.02 ^{bd}	46.82 ± 0.44 ^{bd}
Energy Kcal	386.72	232.00	300.49	318.42	314.18

Values are means ± standard Deviation of triplicate determinations. Values within the same column bearing similar superscript letters are not significantly different at ($p > 0.5$)

Diet 1=65:30:5 Millet, Soybean, Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 2=60:30:10 Millet, Soybean Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 3=55:30:15 Millet, Soybean Banana + Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Mineral Composition

The macro and micro minerals composition of the complementary diets (1-3) was evaluated against Cerelac and maize. The results show that the formulated diets contain substantially higher levels of both

macro- and micro-minerals as compared to Cerelac and maize. Calcium (Ca) Diet 2 (91.22 mg/100g) had the highest calcium content, higher than Cerelac (49.03 mg/100g). Essential for strong bone and teeth formation, muscle contraction, and nerve function in infants.

Magnesium (Mg) Diet 2 (142.81 mg/100g) also showed the highest magnesium content, well above the control diets. Magnesium is important for enzyme activity, energy metabolism, and neuromuscular development.

Sodium (Na) Highest in Diet 2 (18.24 mg/100g). sodium helps to maintain fluid balance, nerve transmission, and muscle function. However, excessive sodium should be avoided in infants.

Phosphorus (P) Highest in Diet 1 (78.33 mg/100g). Works synergistically with calcium in bone mineralization and energy metabolism. Iron (Fe) Diet 3 had the highest iron (0.58 mg/100g). Iron prevents anemia and supports oxygen transport and cognitive development.

Zinc (Zn) Diet 2 (17.73 mg/100g) > Diet 3 (15.71 mg/100g) > Cerelac (11.30 mg/100g). Vital for immune function, tissue repair, and growth.

Copper (Cu) Highest in Cerelac (4.54 mg/100g), but adequate levels were present in formulated diets. Copper supports iron metabolism and nervous system function.

Selenium (Se) Diet 3 (19.41 mg/100g) showed very high selenium compared to Cerelac (0.23 mg/100g). Selenium acts as an antioxidant, protecting cells from oxidative damage.

Nickel (Ni), Cobalt (Co), Chromium (Cr) were present in trace amounts, with cobalt highest in Diet 2 (4.01 mg/100g). Cobalt is important for vitamin B12 synthesis while Chromium is important in glucose metabolism.

Table 3.1a: Macro Mineral Content of Formulated Complementary Diets and Controls

Diets (mg/100g)	Calcium	Magnesium	Sodium	Phosphorus
Cerelac®	49.03±0.01 ^a	17.03±0.01 ^a	6.13±0.01 ^a	2.50±0.01 ^a
Maize	54.51±0.01 ^b	13.72±0.01 ^b	9.14±0.02 ^b	1.94±0.01 ^b
Diet 1	62.63±0.01 ^c	120.32±0.01 ^c	13.31±0.01 ^c	78.33±0.01 ^c
Diet 2	91.22±0.01 ^d	142.81±0.01 ^d	18.24±0.01 ^d	62.40±0.01 ^d
Diet 3	51.44±0.01 ^b	130.94±0.01 ^c	13.70±0.01 ^c	73.44±0.01 ^c

Table 3.1b: Micro Mineral Content of Formulated Complementary Diets and Controls

Diets (mg/100g)	Iron	Zinc	Chromium	Copper	Cobalt	Nickel	Selenium
Cerelac®	0.03±0.01 ^b	11.30±0.01 ^b	0.00±0.00	4.54±0.01 ^d	0.32±0.01 ^b	2.04±0.02 ^b	0.23±0.01 ^b
Maize	0.02±0.01 ^a	5.42±0.01 ^a	0.00±0.00	0.92±0.01 ^c	0.00±0.01 ^a	1.30±0.03 ^a	0.10±0.01 ^a
Diet 1	0.44±0.01 ^d	15.02±0.01 ^c	0.00±0.00	0.70±0.01 ^b	2.91±0.01 ^c	6.74±0.01 ^d	14.40±0.01 ^a
Diet 2	0.43±0.01 ^c	17.73±0.01 ^e	0.00.00	0.44±0.01 ^a	4.01±0.01 ^d	3.01±0.01 ^c	17.32±0.01 ^d
Diet 3	0.58±0.01 ^e	15.71±0.01 ^d	0.00±0.00	0.31±0.01 ^a	2.42±0.01 ^d	2.22±0.01 ^b	19.41±0.01 ^c

Values are means ± standard Deviation of triplicate determinations. Values within the same column bearing similar superscript letters are not significantly different at (p>0.5)

Diet 1=65:30:5 Millet, Soybean, Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 2=60:30:10 Millet, Soybean Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 3=55:30:15 Millet, Soybean Banana + Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Vitamins Composition

The fat- and water-soluble vitamins content of the complementary diets were compared to the vitamin composition of Cerelac and maize. The vitamin contents of the complementary diets showed a

remarkably higher content in the complementary diets. Vitamin B1 (Thiamine) was highest in Diet 3 (0.59 mg/100g). Thiamine aids energy metabolism and brain development.

Vitamin B2 (Riboflavin) was highest in Diet 2 (0.33 mg/100g), Thiamine is essential for energy production and tissue repair. Diet 3 (7.85 mg/100g) was highest in Vitamin B3 (Niacin) which Supports digestive health and skin integrity.

Vitamin B6 (Pyridoxine) was highest in Diet 3 (0.54 mg/100g), Pyridoxine is Vital for amino acid metabolism and nervous system development.

Vitamin B12 ranged from 0.07–0.08 mg/100g across the diets. Vitamin B12 is needed for red blood cell formation and neurological function.

Vitamin C content in Diet 2 (72.65 mg/100g) was significantly higher than Cerelac (49.50 mg/100g). Vitamin C Boosts immunity, enhances iron absorption, and supports tissue repair.

Table 4.1a: Water Soluble Vitamin Composition of Formulated Diets and Controls (mg/100g)

Diets	Vitamin B1	Vitamin B2	Vitamin B3	Vitamin B6	Vitamin B12	Vitamin C
Cerelac	0.27±0.00 ^a	0.15±0.01 ^a	5.01±0.01 ^a	0.40±0.00 ^a	0.08±0.00 ^a	49.50±0.01 ^a
Maize	0.39±0.01 ^{b,c}	0.23±0.00 ^{b,c}	5.23±0.03 ^{b,c}	0.43±0.00 ^{b,c}	0.08±0.00 ^{b,c}	49.24±0.01 ^b
Diet 1	0.35±0.01 ^{b,c}	0.12±0.01 ^{b,d}	7.10±0.06 ^{b,d}	0.53±0.00 ^{b,d}	0.08±0.00 ^{b,d}	49.60±0.01 ^a
Diet 2	0.47±0.01 ^{b,d}	0.33±0.00 ^{b,d}	6.46±0.01 ^{b,d}	0.52±0.00 ^{b,d}	0.07±0.00 ^{b,d}	72.65±0.01 ^c
Diet 3	0.59±0.03 ^{b,d}	0.12±0.00 ^{b,d}	7.85±0.02 ^{b,d}	0.54±0.00 ^{b,d}	0.08±0.00 ^{b,d}	60.43±0.01 ^d

Table 4.1b: Fat Soluble Vitamin Composition of Formulated Diets and Controls (mg/100)

Diets	Vitamins A	Vitamins D	Vitamins E	Vitamins K
Cerelac®	8.11±0.01 ^a	1.68±0.01 ^a	17.96±0.01 ^a	0.24±0.01 ^a
Maize	7.25±0.01 ^b	1.21±0.01 ^b	4.33±0.01 ^b	2.50±0.01 ^b
Diet 1	228.77±0.01 ^c	18.34±0.01 ^c	12.93±0.01 ^c	1.86±0.01 ^c
Diet 2	295.05±0.01 ^d	11.71±0.01 ^d	12.96±0.01 ^c	0.71±0.01 ^d
Diet 3	254.06±0.01 ^d	15.94±0.01 ^c	16.84±0.01 ^a	0.69±0.01 ^d

Values are means ± standard Deviation of triplicate determinations. Values within the same column bearing similar superscript letters are not significantly different at ($p > 0.5$)

Diet 1=65:30:5 Millet, Soybean, Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 2=60:30:10 Millet, Soybean Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 3=55:30:15 Millet, Soybean Banana + Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Fatty Acids Composition of Formulated Diets

The fatty acids analysis of the formulated complementary diet showed that the formulated diets contained both saturated and unsaturated fatty acids as shown in table 22. The diets provided a good balance of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids, including essential fatty acids like linoleic and linolenic acids, crucial for brain development and growth. Arachidonic and eicosapentaenoic acids were also present, supporting immune function.

Total fatty acid content was competitive with Cerelac®, with Diet 3 showing the highest value (107.47±3.44).

Table 2.2: Fatty acids composition of formulated diets

	C12	C14	C16	C18	C18:1	C18:2	C18:3
Cerelac	4.38±0.20 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^a	2.46±0.11 ^a	16.11±0.74 ^a	17.11±0.79 ^a	40.28±1.86 ^a	11.62±0.54 ^a
Maize	1.87±0.09 ^{b,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{b,c}	14.94±0.69 ^{a,c}	8.20±0.38 ^{b,c}	11.34±0.52 ^{b,c}	4.00±0.18 ^{b,c}
Diets 1	2.53±0.12 ^{b,c}	1.10±0.00 ^{a,c}	2.86±0.13 ^{a,d}	14.95±0.69 ^{a,c}	17.68±0.35 ^{b,d}	11.34±0.52 ^{b,c}	4.40±0.20 ^{b,c}
Diets 2	2.56±0.12 ^{b,d}	2.24±0.10 ^{b,d}	3.09±0.14 ^{b,d}	17.99±0.37 ^{b,d}	10.31±0.48 ^{b,d}	17.19±0.79 ^{b,d}	10.22±0.47 ^{a,d}
Diets 3	4.76±0.22 ^{a,d}	0.91±0.04 ^{b,d}	3.09±0.14 ^{b,d}	18.78±0.41 ^{b,d}	19.38±0.43 ^{b,d}	15.12±0.70 ^{b,c}	10.27±0.47 ^{a,d}

Values are means ± standard Deviation of triplicate determinations. Values within the same column bearing similar superscript letters are not significantly different at ($p>0.5$)

Diet 1=65:30:5 Millet, Soybean, Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 2=60:30:10 Millet, Soybean Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 3=55:30:15 Millet, Soybean Banana + Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

	C20:2	C20:3	C20:4	C20:5	C22:6	C24:5	Total
Cerelac	2.58±0.12 ^a	2.65±0.12 ^a	5.19±0.24 ^a	18.75±0.87 ^a	3.43±0.16 ^a	2.01±0.09 ^a	126.57±5.85 ^a
Maize	0.00±0.00 ^{b,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{b,c}	2.34±0.43 ^{b,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{b,c}	3.61±0.17 ^{a,c}	4.73±0.22 ^{b,c}	51.03±2.68 ^{b,c}
Diet 1	2.70±0.02 ^{b,d}	0.01±0.00 ^{b,c}	12.45±0.58 ^{b,d}	8.00±0.00 ^{b,c}	4.62±0.17 ^{a,c}	2.89±0.13 ^{b,d}	85.53±3.20 ^{b,d}
Diet 2	2.01±0.40 ^{a,c}	0.06±0.00 ^{b,c}	9.36±0.00 ^{b,d}	6.82±0.32 ^{b,d}	5.99±0.28 ^{b,d}	2.94±0.14 ^{b,d}	90.78±3.20 ^{b,d}
Diet 3	2.85±0.61 ^{b,d}	0.15±0.00 ^{b,c}	10.02±0.00 ^{b,d}	6.81±0.31 ^{b,d}	12.96±0.60 ^{b,d}	2.37±0.11 ^{a,d}	107.47±3.44 ^{a,c}

Values are means ± standard Deviation of triplicate determinations. Values within the same column bearing similar superscript letters are not significantly different at ($p>0.5$)

Diet 1=65:30:5 Millet, Soybean, Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 2=60:30:10 Millet, Soybean Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 3=55:30:15 Millet, Soybean Banana + Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Amino Acid Composition of Formulated Diet

The result of the amino acids profile of the formulated complementary diet as shown in tables 2.4 and 2.5 below, showed that the formulated diets met and exceeded WHO/FAO essential amino acid requirements. Soybean inclusion corrected lysine deficiencies typically seen in cereal-based diets. Tryptophan and methionine contents were notably improved.

The essential amino acid scores (37.78–41.83 g/100 g protein) were higher than Cerelac® (36.42 g/100 g protein) and maize (33.89 g/100 g protein), indicating superior protein quality.

Non-essential amino acids like proline, arginine, and glutamic acid were present in good amounts, supporting digestion and immunity.

Table 3.1 Essential Amino Acid composition of Formulated Diets

Essential Amino acids (g)	Cerelac	Maize	Diet 1	Diet 2	Diet 3	WHO/FAO
Histidine	2.70±0.08	3.25±0.02	2.78±0.40	3.21±0.02	2.71±0.00	1.9
Isoleucine	3.76±0.10	4.61±0.58	4.40±0.52	4.60±0.07	4.11±0.01	2.8
Leucine	8.30±0.05	10.25±0.16	9.61±0.05	9.82±0.06	9.25±0.04	6.6
Methionine	1.62±0.05	0.10±0.02	2.42±0.05	2.50±0.04	2.30±0.01	1.5
Phenylalanine	5.15±0.04	4.50±0.05	4.40±0.03	4.82±0.06	4.02±0.02	2.8
Threonine	3.56±0.05	3.21±0.02	3.89±0.06	4.76±0.05	4.20±0.03	3.4
Tryptophan	0.90±0.01	0.67±0.03	1.31±0.01	1.39±0.06	1.26±0.04	1.1
Valine	5.22±0.02	4.15±0.04	5.81±0.05	6.01±0.02	5.61±0.08	3.5
Lysine	5.21±0.06	3.15±0.04	4.55±0.40	4.72±0.01	4.32±0.04	5.8
TOTALΣEAAS	36.42±0.47	33.89±0.96	39.17±1.21	41.83±0.39	37.78±0.27	-

Table 3.2: Non-Essential Amino Acid composition of Formulated Diet

Non-Essential Amino acids (g)	Cerelac	Maize	Diet 1	Diet 2	Diet 3	
Proline	3.61±0.05	4.55±0.04	8.85±0.10	9.01±0.04	8.61±0.05	-
Arginine	6.78±0.06	4.63±0.03	5.30±0.04	6.01±0.08	5.41±0.04	-
Tyrosine	3.09±0.03	3.55±0.03	3.76±0.03	3.96±0.05	3.59±0.02	-
Serine	3.19±0.02	3.80±0.01	4.50±0.05	4.95±0.06	4.09±0.05	-
Aspartic acid	9.75±0.04	7.03±0.12	6.88±0.05	7.18±0.05	6.71±0.07	-
Cysteine	1.50±0.03	1.40±0.04	0.49±0.02	0.60±0.01	0.41±0.01	-
Alanine	4.36±0.04	5.01±0.02	6.55±0.04	7.71±0.08	7.35±0.04	-
Glutamic acid	12.45±0.04	14.33±0.02	15.83±0.02	16.45±0.02	15.61±0.01	-
Glycine	3.36±0.05	3.51±0.02	4.55±0.06	3.72±0.02	4.11±0.02	-
ΣNEAAS	48.09±0.36	47.81±0.33	56.71±0.41	59.59±0.41	55.89±0.31	

Values are means ± standard Deviation of triplicate determinations. Values within the same column bearing similar superscript letters are not significantly different at ($p>0.5$)

Diet 1=65:30:5 Millet, Soybean, Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 2=60:30:10 Millet, Soybean Banana+ Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Diet 3=55:30:15 Millet, Soybean Banana + Pumpkin seeds, Sorghum bicolor, Date

Amino Acid Score

The amino acid score (AAS) is a measure used to evaluate the quality of a protein based on its amino acid composition. It compares the amount of each essential amino acid in a protein source to a reference value,

typically derived from human nutritional needs or a reference protein. The total amino acids in the weaning diets ranged from 93.67±1.62 to 101.42±0.80, it is statistically higher when compared to the total amino acids in the reference weaning food cerelac (84.51±0.83).

The total amino acid in the formulated weaning diet ranged from 37.78±0.27 % -41.83±0.39% as compared to cerelac 6.42±0.47. The total non-essential amino acids in the formulated weaning diet ranged from 55.89±0.31% - 59.59±0.41%.

Table 3.3: Essential Amino Acid Score (g/100g protein)

PROLINE	3.61±0.05	4.55±0.04	8.85±0.10	9.01±0.04	8.61±0.05	-
ARGININE	6.78±0.06	4.63±0.03	5.30±0.04	6.01±0.08	5.41±0.04	-
TYROSINE	3.09±0.03	3.55±0.03	3.76±0.03	3.96±0.05	3.59±0.02	-
SERINE	3.19±0.02	3.80±0.01	4.50±0.05	4.95±0.06	4.09±0.05	-
ASPATIC ACID	9.75±0.04	7.03±0.12	6.88±0.05	7.18±0.05	6.71±0.07	-
CYSTEINE	1.50±0.03	1.40±0.04	0.49±0.02	0.60±0.01	0.41±0.01	-
ALANINE	4.36±0.04	5.01±0.02	6.55±0.04	7.71±0.08	7.35±0.04	-
GLUTAMIC ACID	12.45±0.04	14.33±0.02	15.83±0.02	16.45±0.02	15.61±0.01	-
GLYCINE	3.36±0.05	3.51±0.02	4.55±0.06	3.72±0.02	4.11±0.02	-
ΣNEAAS	48.09±0.36	47.81±0.33	56.71±0.41	59.59±0.41	55.89±0.31	

Table 3.4: Non-Essential Amino Acid Score (g/100g)

Essential Amino acids	Cerelac	Maize	Diet 1	Diet 2	Diet 3	WHO/FAO
HISTIDINE	2.70±0.08	3.25±0.02	2.78±0.40	3.21±0.02	2.71±0.00	1.9
ISOLEUCINE	3.76±0.10	4.61±0.58	4.40±0.52	4.60±0.07	4.11±0.01	2.8
LEUCINE	8.30±0.05	10.25±0.16	9.61±0.05	9.82±0.06	9.25±0.04	6.6
METHIONINE	1.62±0.05	0.10±0.02	2.42±0.05	2.50±0.04	2.30±0.01	1.5
PHENYLALANINE	5.15±0.04	4.50±0.05	4.40±0.03	4.82±0.06	4.02±0.02	2.8
THREONINE	3.56±0.05	3.21±0.02	3.89±0.06	4.76±0.05	4.20±0.03	3.4
TRYPTOPHAN	0.90±0.01	0.67±0.03	1.31±0.01	1.39±0.06	1.26±0.04	1.1
VALINE	5.22±0.02	4.15±0.04	5.81±0.05	6.01±0.02	5.61±0.08	3.5
LYSINE	5.21±0.06	3.15±0.04	4.55±0.40	4.72±0.01	4.32±0.04	5.8
TOTALΣEAAS	36.42±0.47	33.89±0.96	39.17±1.21	41.83±0.39	37.78±0.27	-

Protein Digestibility Corrected Amino Acid Score (PDCAAS)

PDCAAS values of the formulated diets (93.67–101.42) as shown in table 2.6 below, were higher than Cerelac® (84.51) and maize (81.61), confirming excellent digestibility and protein quality. The TEAA/TNEAA ratios (0.68–0.70) were similar to Cerelac® (0.76) and maize (0.71), indicating balanced amino acid profiles. Sulfur amino acids (2.71–3.10 g/100 g protein) and aromatic amino acids were comparable to Cerelac®, with higher levels than maize. Arginine-to-lysine ratios (1.16–1.27) aligned with recommended values.

Branched-chain amino acids (18.97–20.43 g/100 g protein) exceeded both Cerelac® (17.28) and the WHO/FAO minimum (10.00), supporting muscle development and energy metabolism.

Table 3.5: Protein Digestibility Amino Acid Score

PDCAAS	Cerelac	Maize	Diet 1	Diet 2	Diet 3	WHO/FAO
TAAS	84.51±0.83	81.61±1.29	95.88±1.62	101.42±0.80	93.67±0.58	
TEAA/TNEAA	0.76±1.31	0.71±2.91	0.69±2.95	0.70±0.95	0.68±0.87	
TEAA/TAA %	0.43±0.57	0.42±74	0.41±0.75	0.41±0.49	0.40±0.47	11-26
∑SAA METH/CYS	3.12±0.08	1.50±0.06	2.91±0.06	3.10±0.05	2.71±0.02	
∑ARAA PHE + TYRO	8.24±0.07	8.50±0.08	8.16±0.06	8.78±0.09	7.61±0.04	
ARGININE/LYS	1.30±1.00	1.47±0.75	1.16±1.00	1.27±0.09	1.25±1.00	1.00

CONCLUSION

The formulated complementary diets showed strong potential as affordable, nutrient-rich alternatives using local ingredients.

Their proximate composition and high protein content, balanced fatty acid profile, and comprehensive amino acid composition make them suitable for improving infant nutrition, particularly in low-resource settings.

Overall, the formulated diets are nutritionally adequate, affordable, and locally accessible alternatives to commercial weaning foods. Though their energy content is slightly lower, it can be easily supplemented with energy-rich foods.

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